

Solar energetic particle analysis platform for the inner heliosphere

SERPENTINE

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List of Acronyms

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
BepiC	BepiColombo
BGO	Bismuth Germanium Oxide
CAU	Christian Albrechts University
CDPU	Common Data Processing Unit
DE	Deflected Electrons
EPAM	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor
EGAM	Gravity Assist Maneuver
EPD	Energetic Particle Detector
EPT	Electron Proton Telescope
ESA	European Space Agency
H2020	Horizon 2020 Framework Programme
HET	High Energy Telescope
ICU	Instrument Control Unit
LVPS	Low-Voltage Power Supply
LEFS60	Low Energy Foil Spectrometer
MCP	Micro-Channel Plate
MPO-MAG	Mercury Planetary Orbiter Magnetometer
MOSIF	Magnetospheric Orbiter Sunshield and Interface Structure
PSP	Parker Solar Probe
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SERPENTINE	Solar Energetic Particle Analysis Platform for the Inner Heliosphere
S/C	spacecraft
SIS	Suprathermal Ion Spectrograph
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SoIO	Solar Orbiter
STEP	SupraThermal Electrons and Protons
STEREO	Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the data validation and verification strategy for the high level data products provided by the Solar Energetic Particle Analysis Platform for the Inner Heliosphere ([SERPENTINE](#)) project. It covers the identification of data issues present in current public data products, which are candidates for correction in higher level data sets, the implementation of correction or mitigation procedures, cross-calibrations with other instruments and the verification procedures previous to public release.

1 Introduction

The **SERPENTINE** project funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme (**H2020**) of the European Union focuses on the investigation of the origin and properties of large and widespread Solar Energetic Particle (**SEP**) events related to solar flares and coronal mass ejections. The project analyzes data from several heliospheric observatories, with particular attention to recent missions exploring the innermost part of the heliosphere such as Solar Orbiter (**Solo**), BepiColombo (**BepiC**) and Parker Solar Probe (**PSP**). **SERPENTINE** will generate new high-level data products, catalogs and visualizations derived from the observations. These results will be publicly distributed for their exploitation by the whole heliophysics community. They can be divided into two different categories: catalogs and other level 3 data products resulting from the enhanced analysis of existing level 2 data sets.

1.1 Purpose and objectives

This document describes the data validation and verification strategy for the new level 3 data products that will be produced by **SERPENTINE** using energetic particle data from the Energetic Particle Detector (**EPD**) instrument suite onboard Solar Orbiter and the Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer (**SIXS**) instrument onboard BepiColombo. This includes the identification of instrumental issues affecting the level 2 data sets which could be corrected in the level 3 data (or in new versions of the level 2 data), the development and implementation of correction or mitigation procedures, the comparison with observations from instruments onboard different spacecraft in order to obtain cross-calibrations, and the definition of data verification procedures prior to the public release of the level 3 data products.

1.2 EPD instrument description

EPD is an instrument suite comprising different sensors that have been designed to measure the spectra, composition, time variations, and directional distributions of energetic particles. These measurements are performed over a partly overlapping energy range encompassing a few keV to 450 MeV/n, with sufficient time, energy, angular, and mass resolution to achieve the mission science goals. **EPD** consists of the following units:

- **SupraThermal Electrons and Protons (STEP)**. Designed to measure protons and electrons at supra-thermal energies (between 2 and ~ 80 keV). It employs two co-aligned sensor heads with a parallel field of view. One of the sensor heads contains a permanent magnet that deflects electrons out of the nominal field of view, this is referred to as *magnet* channel and measures all types of particles except electrons. The other head measures every particle in the energy range including electrons and is called *integral* channel. Each head contains a solid-state detector divided in several pixels to achieve angular resolution. For each channel there are 15 pixels distributed in 3 rows and 5 columns, plus a separate pixel for measuring background.
- **Electron Proton Telescope (EPT)**. **EPT** measures electrons and ions (mostly protons) in the lower energy part of the energetic particle spectrum (25–500 keV for electrons and from 25 keV to few MeV for ions). It relies on the magnet/foil technique adapted from STEREO/SEPT to separate electrons and ions. **EPT** consists of 2 double-ended telescopes providing 4 fields of view. Each telescope end has 2 channels, one of them is equipped with a set of magnets deflecting electrons and measures only ions, the other channel contains a foil that stops ions with energies below ~ 400 keV while leaving the electron spectrum unchanged in the measured range.

- **Suprathermal Ion Spectrograph (SIS).** SIS provides observations of multiple species between H-Fe between energies just above the solar wind to multiple MeV/nucleon energies. SIS consists of 2 telescopes (SIS-A and SIS-B) pointing in different directions and sharing the same electronics box. SIS is able to identify ion species by measuring the time of flight of the particles that enter in the detector, as well as its energy, thus providing an indirect measure of their mass.
- **High Energy Telescope (HET).** HET measures electrons, protons and heavy ions and covers the upper energy end of the EPD range. There are two HET units, each consisting of a double-sided telescope and an electronics box which is shared with EPT. Consequently, it provides measurements in four distinct fields of view (the same as EPT). Each telescope contains two solid state detectors (A and B) for each direction and a shared Bismuth Germanium Oxide (BGO) scintillator (C). Measuring the characteristics of the energy deposition in the different detectors, HET is able to identify particle species in a wide energy range.
- **Instrument Control Unit (ICU).** The ICU is the interface between the spacecraft and the EPD sensors. All EPD sensors are connected to the ICU, which provides them with a telecommand and telemetry communication link, time synchronization, processing and power. It consists of a Common Data Processing Unit (CDPU) and a Low-Voltage Power Supply (LVPS), operating in a cold redundant configuration.

STEP, EPT, and HET were developed by the Christian Albrechts University (CAU) of Kiel, Germany. SIS was developed by the Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory and CAU. The ICU was developed by the PI institution at the University of Alcalá, Spain. The location of the different EPD sensor units on the spacecraft is shown in Fig. 1. EPT and HET sensors are located on two almost identical units: EPT-HET1 and EPT-HET2, each covering two opposed fields of view (sun-antisun and north-south respectively). Figures 2 and 3 show the energy coverage and observed fields of view of EPD respectively.

Figure 1: Solar Orbiter spacecraft showing the location of the different EPD sensor units. In the coordinate system of this figure, +X points towards the Sun and the Y and Z complete the orthogonal basis. The left side shows a view of the -Y panel showing the sensors oriented along the mean Parker spiral direction, and the right side shows the view of the +Y panel (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020).

Figure 2: Energy coverage of the EPD sensors for different species (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020).

Figure 3: Fields of view of the EPD sensors in the spacecraft reference frame. The colour-coded plot shows the hourly averaged magnetic-field distribution as observed by HELIOS-1 (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020).

1.3 BepiColombo SIXS instrument description

BepiC / SIXS (Huovelin et al. 2020) contains a multi-layer particle telescope that has a single CsI(Tl) scintillator (with dimensions of $5 \times 5 \times 6.3 \text{ mm}^3$) with a photodiode readout surrounded by (150- μm -thick) silicon detectors from five sides (Fig. 4). This detection system is called SIXS-P. The scintillator is called 'core detector' and the silicon detectors are called 'side detectors' and numbered as Side 0, Side 1, ..., Side 4 with Side 0 being the one pointing upwards and the others pointing sideways around Side 0 (in instrument coordinates). Each of the five passively collimated apertures is covered by two foils: 7 μm of beryllium followed by 7 μm of Kapton. The foils stop protons at $<1 \text{ MeV}$ energies but pass electrons at much lower energies. With a detection threshold in the Si detectors of about 35 keV deposited energy, the incident-energy detection threshold is about 50 keV for electrons and about 1 MeV for protons. Electrons will pass to the scintillator at energies $>300 \text{ keV}$ and protons at

Figure 4: SIXS-P sensor head. The left figure provides a cross-section of the detector and the right figure a photo showing the mounting of the sensor head on top of the SIXS instrument.

energies >4.3 MeV. The scintillator is thick enough to stop protons at 30 MeV and electrons at several MeV energies. The instrument, thus, uses the measurement below the foil at the lowest energies (at 50–300 keV for electrons and 1–4.3 MeV for protons) and the ΔE – E technique at higher energies.

The silicon detectors have two active areas: the central circular area located below the aperture is used as the actual detector and the surrounding area as an anti-coincidence shield. On the sixth side of the scintillator is the photodiode reading out its signal. The scintillator has a detection threshold of about 500 keV, which makes the response of the detector to electrons, in particular, a rather complicated function of energy. The nominal energy ranges for electrons and protons are 50–3000 keV and 1–30 MeV, respectively. There are nominally six (eight) differential electron (proton) channels and one integral channel for both species. The response functions of the electron and proton channels to the species they are nominally measuring are given in Fig. 5. The narrow lowest-energy proton channels P1–P2 are also responding to electrons and can be used as electron channels when protons are absent from the environment.

SIXS-P data analysis relies on the so-called bow-tie analysis, which determines the effective energy and geometric factor of each detection channel by utilising simulated response function, $R_{s,k}(E)$, of the channel k , and the resulting counting rate due to particles of species s , obtained as

$$CR_{s,k} = \int_0^{\infty} j_s(E) R_{s,k}(E) dE, \quad (1)$$

where $j_s(E)$ is the (omnidirectional) differential intensity of species s . The counting rate is converted into intensity by dividing with the product of the geometric factor $G_{s,k}$ and energy channel width $\Delta E_{s,k}$. For a power-law spectrum, $j_s(E) = AE^{-\gamma}$, the equation yields

$$AE_{k,s,\text{eff}}^{-\gamma} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} AE^{-\gamma} R_{s,k}(E) dE}{G_{s,k} \Delta E_{s,k}}, \quad (2)$$

where $E_{k,s,\text{eff}}$ is the effective energy of species s in the channel k . Hence, the conversion factor of the counting rate to intensity can be given as

$$G_{s,k} \Delta E_{s,k} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} E^{-\gamma} R_{s,k}(E) dE}{E_{k,s,\text{eff}}^{-\gamma}}. \quad (3)$$

Figure 5: SIXS-P response to electrons (left) and protons (right) per aperture. While the proton energy channels P1–P8 are rather nominal differential energy channels with box-car-like response functions, electron channels have more complicated responses.

Thus, each pair of effective energy and spectral index γ will yield a value for the conversion factor. The bow-tie analysis considers a range of spectral indices and effective energies and chooses the value of energy that minimises the spread of $G_{s,k} \Delta E_{s,k}$ for the chosen range of spectral indices. For the bow-tie analysis of SIXS detection channels, we have considered spectral indices $\gamma \in [1.5, 3.5]$ and obtained the effective energies along with the flux conversion factors and their systematic uncertainties within this range of spectra.

2 Level 3 datasets

Level 3 data are high-level data products derived from the combination of several level 2 datasets or from the analysis of data included in one or more level 2 datasets.

EPD level 3 datasets produced by SERPENTINE may include:

- Data files with different cadences and energy resolutions than those included in level 2 data.
- Higher level corrections derived from a deeper analysis of the data (e.g. removal of ion contamination of electron channels).
- Scientific parameters derived in combination with other instruments, as for example pitch angles, in combination with the Solar Orbiter Magnetometer (MAG).
- Plots combining different instruments/sensors (e.g. pitch angle distributions, combined dynamic spectra, combined energetic particle, plasma and magnetic field data, etc.).
- Any other product that may result from the analysis of EPD data.

SIXS-P level-3 data produced by SERPENTINE may include:

- Data files with different cadences and energy resolutions than those included in level 2 data.
- Higher level corrections derived from a deeper analysis of the data (e.g. ion channels interpreted as electron channels for the use during electron-rich time periods).
- Scientific parameters derived in combination with other instruments, as for example pitch angles, in combination with the BepiC / Mercury Planetary Orbiter Magnetometer (MPO-MAG).

- Plots combining different instruments/sensors (e.g. pitch angle distributions, combined dynamic spectra, combined energetic particle and magnetic field data, etc.).
- Any other product that may result from the analysis of [SIXS](#) data.

3 Identification of instrumental issues

3.1 Solar Orbiter EPD/STEP instrumental issues

3.1.1 Particle separation

As stated in section 1.2, the [STEP](#) sensor consists of two similar detectors, the so-called *integral* and *magnet* channels. The *magnet* channel is equipped with a permanent magnet that deflects electrons and measures only ions, while the *integral* channel measures all types of particles. This design allows for the separation of electrons and ions by looking at the difference between the measured intensities in both channels, although there are some caveats:

- Due to the statistical properties of particle detections that follow a Poisson distribution, during periods of high ion flux, the natural fluctuations of the ion measurements are propagated to the calculated electron intensities. This may produce very low signal-to-noise ratios for electrons during large ion events that may even lead to negative instantaneous electron intensities when the electron flux is sufficiently low.
- The instrument response for ions is slightly different for the *integral* and *magnet* channels. The design of [STEP](#) includes a small offset in the pinhole serving as an entrance to the *magnet* channels detector that compensates for the deviation induced by the magnet. However, given that this deviation depends on the energy and the ion species, it cannot be completely removed. For protons, a precise intercalibration of the two channels can mitigate this effect, however, when the measured intensities have contributions from several ion species this mitigation might not be possible.

We should note that these caveats only apply when the ion contribution to measured intensities is large. During electron-dominated periods, the procedure to recover electron intensities by comparing the *integral* and *magnet* channels gives very good results.

The design of [STEP](#) does not allow, in principle, for the separation of different ion species.

3.1.2 Contamination by high energy particles

Figure 6: Combined dynamic spectrum of STEP ions, EPT ions and HET protons showing contamination by high energy particles in STEP and EPT (marked by a red ellipse).

High energy particles can penetrate the housing of STEP and produce a signal in the detector that is indistinguishable from that of the particles in the nominal energy range. During highly energetic particle events, this effect can produce a noticeable contamination in the STEP measurements. For instance, figure 6 shows clearly this effect on STEP and EPT during an SEP event showing ion velocity dispersion (the contamination effect is marked by a red ellipse in figure 6). Each of the STEP channels contains a background pixel that could be used to correct for this effect, although its reliability is still under study.

3.1.3 Compton-Getting effect

STEP level 2 data includes calibrated intensities and energies given in the spacecraft (S/C) reference frame. However, a proper analysis of the particle pitch angles, taking advantage of the pixelated detector, must always be done in the reference frame of the solar wind. The relative velocity between the S/C and the solar wind is not large enough to produce a significant effect in the electron measurements of STEP, but this is not the case for ions. Unfortunately, given that STEP measures total energy (and not energy per mass, which can be directly associated with velocity), the change of reference frame will have a different effect for different ion species, that cannot be separated in the STEP measurements. Thus, a systematic correction of the Compton-Getting effect is not possible for STEP ion data, and it might only be done in a case by case basis, by assuming certain properties of the data (as for example the relative abundances of the different ions).

3.1.4 Detector dead times

The dead time is the time after each particle detection during which the sensor is not able to record another event. For moderate particle fluxes, the total dead time produced by the accumulation of all particle events is still negligible compared with the total integration time. However for large events, the fraction of dead time may be significant, reducing the effective integration time and thus the number counts detected. Moreover, for very high intensities, multiple particle effects, such as pile-ups, can further reduce the count rate.

By the time of writing this document, there is no correction for dead times in the level 2 STEP data.

However, the affected periods are indicated in the quality flag according to the following criteria:

- Periods with dead time fraction over 10% are marked with a reduced quality flag.
- Data from periods with dead time fraction over 25% are removed from the level 2 data.

A dead time correction is currently under investigation by the EPD team and may be included in future versions of the level 2 and level 3 STEP data.

Figure 7 shows a comparison between STEP and EPT measurements for a period when STEP is affected by large dead times.

Figure 7: Comparison between EPT and STEP data during a period affected by large dead times. *Top:* Comparison of the ion intensities measured by STEP and EPT in the same energy range, showing a significant drop in STEP measured intensities during periods with large dead times. *Middle:* Combined dynamic spectrum of STEP and EPT. *Bottom:* Value of the quality flag included in level 2 STEP data.

3.1.5 Stray light

Certain configurations of the solar array panels of Solar Orbiter have been found to produce stray light on the integral channel detector of STEP. This can be seen as a sudden increase of the count rate in some of the integral channel pixels when the solar panel angle changes from 0 to 10 degrees or vice versa (see figure 8).

Figure 8: Effect of stray light in the count rate measured by some pixels of the STEP integral channel produced by the movement of the solar panels. *Top:* Solar array angle as a function of time. *Bottom:* Count rate measured by pixels 6, 11 and 12 of STEP's integral channel.

The affected periods, which do not last more than a couple of minutes each, are already identified and flagged accordingly in the level 2 STEP data.

3.1.6 Ion energy calibration issues

Figure 9: *Left:* Dynamic spectrum measured by pixel 3 of STEP during an ion event with very low scattering. *Right:* The same event as measured by STEP pixel 13. The energy measured by pixel 3 is lower than the one measured by pixel 13, as can be seen by comparing the tracks produced by protons during the event. The track visible in the upper part of the left panel is probably due to helium.

During some events, it has been found that some pixels of STEP are measuring ion energies that are lower than expected. This can be seen when comparing with EPT measurements in the overlapping range and with other STEP pixels, as can be seen in figure 9. It affects pixels observing closest to the Sun direction, for which the particle flux coming from the solar wind has been substantially larger throughout the mission, suggesting that it could be due to ageing of the detector. This issue has not been observed for electrons.

Possible correction or mitigation of this effect is still under investigation.

3.2 Solar Orbiter EPD/EPT instrumental issues

3.2.1 Ion contamination in the electron telescopes

The electron telescopes of EPT are equipped with a foil that blocks protons with energies below ~ 400 keV. However, protons (and other ions) with energies above this value can penetrate the foil and deposit part of their energy in the detector. This produces contamination in EPT electron measurements whenever there is a significant flux of protons between ~ 400 and ~ 750 keV (protons with energies above ~ 750 keV no longer deposit energy in the nominal range of EPT).

3.2.2 Contamination by high energy particles

EPT uses an anti-coincidence filter to reduce the background noise generated by cosmic rays that penetrate the main detector. However, some particles above the nominal energy range can still lose some energy in the passive parts of the sensor and produce a valid signal in the detector. Figure 6 shows an example of contamination by high energy particles in EPT during a large event.

3.3 Solar Orbiter EPD/SIS instrumental issues

3.3.1 Operation of the MCP high voltage

During certain S/C manoeuvres, Micro-Channel Plate (MCP) high voltage is lowered down for protecting SIS from possible contamination caused by the platform thrusters. This operation reduces the sensitivity of the instrument depending on the exact value of the voltage applied. The periods affected are flagged accordingly in level 2 SIS data.

Since March 2023, the analysis of the instrument performance has demonstrated that this operation is no longer needed and MCP high voltage is only operated during switch-on and switch-off of SIS.

3.3.2 Periods with high background

During extremely large events, some background excess can be clearly seen in the data, particularly affecting the measured rates of rare ion species. A flag is included in level 2 SIS data to signal this issue.

3.4 Solar Orbiter EPD/HET instrumental issues

At the time of writing this document, there are some inconsistencies in the calibration of HET data between the particles stopping in the first two detectors and those penetrating the BGO crystal. This is currently being investigated by the EPD team and may require a correction in level 2 data. If any further correction or mitigation strategy is required, it will be implemented in level 3 data.

3.5 BepiColombo SIXS instrumental issues

Also BepiC / SIXS-P data has some quality issues that the user needs to take into account. Some of the issues affect the data over the whole time period and some are limited to certain periods of time.

Firstly, while SIXS instrument performs cruise science measurement aboard BepiC, it does not have a 100% duty cycle. Thus, there are multiple long data gaps in the measurements that cannot be recovered. Shorter data gaps arise from anomalies of the instrument data processing unit that seem to be related to cosmic-ray induced single event effects and sometimes lead to a spontaneous booting of the instrument to STANDBY mode. In those cases, recovery to SCIENCE mode may take up to

Figure 10: SIXS-P observations of electron and proton fluxes during an event in March 2023 showing time periods of proton contamination in electron channels (in particular on 2023-03-13) and electron contamination in proton channel P1 (between 2023-03-14T18:00 and 2023-03-16T12:00). The channel PE1 in the lower panel is P1 but normalised with the geometric factor derived from the electron response function.

two days depending on the contemporary operations of the spacecraft.

During the cruise phase of the [BepiColombo](#) mission, [SIXS-P](#) does not have an unobstructed view to space. Sides 0 and 4 have obstructions due to Magnetospheric Orbiter Sunshield and Interface Structure ([MOSIF](#)), which blocks the view of Side 4 entirely and about 20% of the field of view of Side 0. The partial blockage of Side 0 is taken into account in the response function of the view cone, but some additional scattered flux from [MOSIF](#) may appear in its counting rate, especially due to electrons. Side 4 sees only back-scattered flux from [MOSIF](#). The back-scattered particles are dominated by electrons, which can also be used to deduce the composition of primary particles in the environment during periods of cross-species contamination in the energy channels.

After June 2021, there has been a persistent problem with bursts of noise in the Side 3 silicon detector signal. This has led to the elimination of this side detector from the logic. For most of the [SEP](#) events observed by [SIXS](#), only Sides 0, 1, and 2 provide science grade data.

Electrons in particular have complicated response functions (see [Fig. 5](#)). The effective energies and flux conversion factors of the channels have been computed for power-law spectra that decrease with energy. However, in the onset-phase of [SEP](#) events, in particular, the spectrum may not be of the assumed form, but could even miss the low-energies entirely due to velocity dispersion. This means that the response in the channels is at much higher energies than the effective energy of the channel. Therefore, we caution the user about the [SIXS-P](#) electron data in the onset phase of the event to take into account that all channels may actually observe significantly higher energies than indicated by the effective energy of the channels.

Because [SIXS-P](#), at the lowest energies (<300 keV for electrons and <4.3 MeV for protons), relies on detecting particles below foils with a single detector layer, the instrument is prone to cross-species contamination. Electron channels E1–E4 respond to protons of about 1 MeV and proton channels P1 and P2 to electrons at >300 keV energy. [Fig. 10](#) shows an example of cross-species contamination

Figure 11: SIXS-P observations of electron fluxes during the Earth flyby of BepiC in 2020. In the outer belt (at 0:30–3:00 and 5:30–12:00 UT) the PE1 and PE2 channels extend the electron spectral measurement (effective energies 0.47 and 0.88 MeV, respectively), but in the inner belt, where protons dominate the fluxes, PE2 channel has much higher intensity values than PE1, which is an indication not to use PE channels as electron channels.

with an event observed by SIXS on 12–16 March 2023. During the first peak the spectrum of electrons shows a peculiar form with channels E2–E4 observing very similar intensities while E5 observes no increase. This is characteristic of the increase in the electron channels E2–E4 being caused by 1-MeV protons. Similarly, in the later phase of the event, proton channel P1 shows an increase which is much greater than the increase in P2, although their effective energies are very close to one another. This is characteristic of P1 response being mostly to >300 keV-electrons.

During times when there is no 1-MeV protons in the environment (e.g., often during the onset phases of the SEP events), the channels P1 and P2 can be used as electron channels. We have performed bow-tie analysis of them assuming that the particles being counted are electrons. These channels, normalised with electron flux conversion factors, are denoted by PE1 and PE2, and can be used in the analysis to provide two extra electron channels between E4 and E5, as long as care is taken that protons are not present in abundance. The lower panel of Fig. 10 shows also the PE1 channel and the time period where P1 is not consistent with observing the proton intensity (from 2023-03-14T18:00 onward) is also a period where PE1, with its effective energy close to the geometric mean of E4 and E5, shows an intensity consistent with the other electron channels.

Finally, SIXS-P employs an automatic increase of detector thresholds to avoid getting saturated during the largest SEP events (or by large fluxes of Hermean electrons in orbit around Mercury). So far, the thresholds have increased only during the Earth flyby (Fig. 11). As a result of the increase, SIXS electron channels will be either entirely eliminated or their recorded counting rates will be diminished by a large factor. The first threshold increase will eliminate electron channels E1 and E2 from the data, the second will take out E3 and significantly decrease the response in E5–E7, and the third step will eliminate all electron channels from the measurements. The flyby data demonstrates some uncertainties in the response function of E4 after the second step, which are being investigated. The flyby also provided an excellent opportunity to test the PE1 and PE2 channels in the outer belt, where the fluxes are dominated by electrons. They also show that in a proton-dominated environment (the inner belt), PE2 intensities are significantly higher than PE1 intensities, thus demonstrating a way to distinguish situations with and without cross-species contamination.

4 Correction and mitigation procedures

The philosophy behind level 3 data is that they must be ready-to-use without requiring an advanced knowledge of the instrument by the user. For that reason, some strategies should be implemented to correct or mitigate the instrumental issues presented in section 3 and any other problem found in the data during the course of the mission. These strategies will include to:

- Provide flags to inform the user when the quality of the data may be degraded.
- Remove bad data samples.
- Remove energy channels with dubious calibration (typically at the lower end of the spectrum) or combine them to make them more reliable.
- Include corrected data when possible.

Most of the EPD instrumental issues presented in section 3 are already identified and flagged in the EPD level 2 data. These flags will also be included in level 3 data, adding new ones when necessary.

An example of correction that will be included in level 3 data is the removal of ion contamination in EPT electron measurements, which is depicted in figure 12. As mentioned in section 3.2.1 electron measurements in EPT can be contaminated by protons that penetrate the protecting foil in the electron channel. The response of the electron channel to different ion species is known from simulations of the instrument and can be used to estimate the contamination using the ion intensities measured by the magnet (ion) channel EPT. There are, however, some additional considerations that we have to take into account:

- Contamination is mainly due to protons. Helium and heavier ion species do not produce a noticeable contamination in the electron data, but are however present in the ion measurements used to estimate the correction. Nevertheless, the different response of the foil and magnet channels to different ions can be used to infer the fraction of protons in the ion data and reduce the correction accordingly. Specifically, we use some auxiliary bins in the electron channel outside the nominal range that are no longer sensitive to electrons and are dominated by protons.
- The analysis of highly contaminated periods is used to verify the performance of the contamination correction. This has allowed us to detect small differences between the simulated response to protons in the electron channel, used to estimate the contamination, and the actual response. These deviations are quantified and are included in the final correction.

More details about this and other corrections will be given in separate technical notes.

The Level-3 dataset for SIXS-P will contain the PE1 and PE2 channels at those times that they seem to be responding primarily to electrons. The user still needs to realise that the channels might contain an amount of protons and treat the data with some care. Time periods where the data might be saturated despite the increase of the detection thresholds will be removed from the data. The time resolution for the Level-3 product will be two minutes, and the sectorized data will come with the pitch angles of the boresight direction of each view cone, computed using MPO-MAG data. Details of the data products and algorithms used to process the data will be reported in a separate technical note. However, in the following we illustrate a method to assess the electron and proton contributions in P1 channel during the period depicted in Fig. 10.

Since the electron response in P2 is much weaker than in P1, we can often assume that while P1 is contaminated by electrons, P2 is not. Therefore, as the effective energies of P1 and P2 are very close to one another, we can use P2 and P3 to estimate the proton-generated flux in P1. If we assume a

Figure 12: Example of decontamination of EPT electron data. *Top panel:* Original EPT electron data affected by contamination from ions. *Second panel:* EPT ion measurements, showing the energy range of the particles causing contamination in the electron channel. *Third panel:* Model of the ion contamination in the electron data, calculated from ion data. *Bottom panel:* Corrected electron data.

power-law energy spectrum, we can compute the proton intensity at the effective proton energy of P1 as

$$I_{P1'} = I_{P2}(E_{P1}/E_{P2})^\gamma, \quad (4)$$

where the spectral index can be obtained from P2 and P3 as

$$\gamma = \frac{\ln(I_{P2}/I_{P3})}{\ln(E_{P2}/E_{P3})}. \quad (5)$$

During times when $I_{P1'}$ and I_{P1} show consistent intensities, we can be rather confident that the response in P1 is due to protons. However, when the intensities differ so that $I_{P1} > I_{P1'}$, the excess is most likely due to electrons. We can estimate the electron fraction in the channel counts by

$$R_e = \frac{I_{P1} - I_{P1'}}{I_{P1}} \quad (6)$$

and use this to compute the corrected electron intensity in PE1 as

$$I_{PE1'} = \frac{I_{P1} - I_{P1'}}{I_{P1}} I_{PE1}. \quad (7)$$

This method has been applied in Fig. 13. We can clearly see that P1 and P1' are consistent during the first increase in P1 but strongly departing in the second half of the time period. We also see that while small electron fractions cannot be recovered from the channel, there is a meaningful electron measurement available in PE1' during times when electron counts are a sizeable fraction of the proton counts, as evidenced by the similarity of PE1' and E5 channels. Based on the same methodology we can also assess whether protons contaminate channels E1–E4 and flag time periods when they are not counting real electrons. (Proton energies in these channels are also close to 1 MeV.)

5 Cross-calibration activities

5.1 EPD Cross-calibration with near-Earth spacecraft

The understanding of widespread SEP events necessarily entails investigation and quantitative comparison of measurements of energetic particle fluxes by in situ detectors onboard two or more spacecraft at different locations. These instruments comprise a variety of detection techniques, geometries, viewing cones, background levels, etc. They also have made use of different analog and digital electronics. All these factors sometimes lead to noticeable differences in their response to energetic particle fluxes. For this reason, before analyzing and interpreting multiple SEP observations from different spacecraft it is pertinent to ensure that they are directly comparable using cross-calibration procedures.

In order to perform a cross-calibration of two particle detectors onboard different spacecraft, they must be as closely located in space as possible. Additionally, the occurrence of a particle increase above the background flux levels over a wide energy range is required to achieve a meaningful comparison with reasonable counting rate statistics. Finally, the two viewing directions should be covering similar range of pitch-angles or the observed fluxes should be as isotropic as possible in order to minimize differences in the incident flux. It is also advisable to use those periods when the fluxes are expected to show less spatial variations, such as the decay phases of gradual SEP events dominated by the "reservoir effect" (Reames 1999). These factors greatly limit the opportunities for cross calibrations for spacecraft following very different orbits that seldom approach, such as Solar Orbiter and STEREO-A. Figure 14 shows a selection of close approaches of several spacecraft pairs during the period 2021-2024.

Figure 13: Top: Comparison of SIXS proton channel P1 with P1' computed using proton channels P2 and P3. The difference between the channels P1 and P1' represents electron contamination in P1. Bottom: Comparison of the SIXS proton channel P1 normalized as an electron channel, PE1, with a corrected channel PE1' that removes the true proton counts (as estimated by P1') from the data and with electron channels E4 and E5. E4 is contaminated by protons but E5, which is based on a coincidence measurement, is not.

Figure 14: Selection of time periods with close approaches of different pairs of s/c. In each case the distance in au vs time is shown. Observations near these dates can provide opportunities for cross calibrations of the particle instruments onboard.

Panel (b) in figure 14 shows the close approach of Solar Orbiter to the Earth during the Gravity Assist Maneuver (EGAM) at the end of November 2021. This approach offers an opportunity for cross calibration of Solar Orbiter EPD and the particle instrument onboard missions such as Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE), Wind or Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO). The top panel in figure 15 shows the locations of near-Earth spacecraft and Solar Orbiter on December 9, 2021 and the Solar Orbiter trajectory during December 1-9, 2021. The bottom panel shows near-relativistic electron intensities observed by Solar Orbiter EPD-EPT, ACE Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor (EPAM) Deflected Electrons (DE), ACE EPAM Low Energy Foil Spectrometer (LEFS60) and Wind 3DP during a series of electron events observed during this period. A series of solar electron events observed simultaneously by all the spacecraft offer the opportunity to compare the spectra and perform a cross-calibration. Figure 16 shows the electron spectra obtained during a section of the decay phase of the last electron event, with the pre-event background subtracted. The periods used to sample the background and the spectrum are marked by yellow and salmon shaded rectangles in figure 15. A direct comparison of the spectra can be used to obtain cross-calibration factors at different energies.

Figure 15: Top: Locations of Solar Orbiter and near-Earth spacecraft during the period following the EGAM. The dotted line marks the Solar Orbiter trajectory and the solid circles mark the locations at the end of the period. Bottom: near-relativistic electron intensities observed during the same time interval. The shaded yellow bar marks the period used to sample the pre-event background and the shaded salmon area marks the period used to produce the electron spectrum in figure 16.

Figure 16: Electron spectra observed by particle instruments onboard ACE, Wind and Solar Orbiter in a period close to the EGAM (pre-event background has been subtracted in order to remove the effect of the different background levels for each instrument).

We grouped EPT energy bins to replicate as close as possible energy intervals covered by ACE EPAM DE, ACE EPAM LEFS60 and Wind 3DP. Cross-calibration factors are then obtained as the ratio between the spectral points observed by each instrument (after the pre-event background has been subtracted), as shown in figure 17 for EPT and LEFS60. The cross-calibration factors obtained with this methodology are summarized in table 1.

Figure 17: Comparison of EPT and EPAM LEFS60 electron spectra used to obtain cross-calibration factors. The time interval covers a section of the decay phase of a SEP event observed on December 6, 2021, with nearly isotropic fluxes and free of proton contamination. Pre-event background spectrum has been subtracted for both instruments.

Table 1: Cross-calibration factors obtained during the Solar Orbiter EGAM

Channel ratio	value
EPT (38.2-54.2 keV) / DE30 (38-53 keV)	0.74
EPT (54.2-102.1 keV) / DE30 (53-103 keV)	1.04
EPT (110.7-169.0 keV) / DE30 (103-175 keV)	0.59
EPT (46.7-63.5 keV) / LEFS60 (45-62 keV)	0.59
EPT (63.5-102.1 keV) / LEFS60 (62-102 keV)	0.78
EPT (102.1-169.0 keV) / LEFS60 (102-175 keV)	0.81
EPT (184.9-282.6 keV) / LEFS60 (175-290 keV)	0.86
EPT (50.5-86.6 keV) / 3DP SST (51.5-84.7 keV)	0.58
EPT (86.6-143.2 keV) / 3DP SST (84.7-140.4 keV)	0.52
EPT (143.2-237.9 keV) / 3DP SST (140.4-237.2 keV)	0.46

We aim to perform this kind of comparison for other periods when two or more spacecraft are closely spaced. Cross-calibrations of the different particle instruments onboard current missions such as Solar Orbiter, Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory ([STEREO](#)), near-Earth spacecraft ([ACE](#), [SOHO](#), [Wind](#)), BepiColombo and [PSP](#), are an important part of the data validation activities to be performed by [SERPENTINE](#). This comprises the search for suitable time windows based on the orbital data, the identification of active periods within or as near as possible to these times, and the comparison of the spectra in order to derive cross-calibration factors.

5.2 SIXS Cross-calibration activities

So far, [SIXS](#) has not been on during any of the particle events observed in close vicinity of another spacecraft, so cross-calibration activities are still pending. We will monitor the opportunities with [Solo](#) and [PSP](#) and make use of them when they occur.

6 Verification and data release

The overall quality of the data will be inspected routinely before release. This will be done primarily by visual inspection, checking the consistency of the data and comparing measurements taken by different sensors. Information from additional sources, such as housekeeping data from the instrument and the spacecraft, will also be used to identify potential issues.

The first release of Solar Orbiter / [EPD](#) level 3 data is based on the last version of level 2 data available. Subsequent releases may be needed whenever a new version of level 2 data is produced.

The [BepiC](#) / [SIXS](#) level 3 data release had some delays because of the formatting and data policy requirements of the mission that the team had to follow. The final file format (CSV for data and XML for metadata) has been iterated with European Space Agency ([ESA](#)) and the production of the data files in their final format has started. After their verification by the UTU team and the Agency, they can be ingested in [ESA](#)'s Planetary Science Archive and released in the [SERPENTINE](#) Project Data Centre. We expect the data to be available for the community by the end of September 2024.

7 Conclusions and Outlook

The **SERPENTINE** project will produce new Solar Orbiter **EPD** and BepiColombo **SIXS** level 3 data sets with added scientific value. These data will include corrections for several instrumental issues such as ion contamination of the electron channels and new products derived from multiple data sets such as pitch-angle distributions. This document summarizes several known instrumental issues affecting **EPD** and **SIXS** data, and describes the general level 3 strategy for data correction, validation and verification. It also explains the procedure to cross-calibrate particle instruments onboard different missions.

As the solar cycle continues its progression and larger **SEP** events can be expected in the upcoming months, the **SERPENTINE** team will have the opportunity to further investigate these issues, improve the characterization of the instrument response under very high flux conditions and test the correction procedures.

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